

Connect among Green, Sustainable and Hotel Industry: A Prospective Simulation Study

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Abstract : This review paper aims at understanding the importance of implementing sustainable green practices in the current hotel industry and the perception of the same from the point of view of the customers as well as the industry experts. Many hotels have benefited from green management such as enhanced reputation of the firm and more worth customers. For the business standing, it reduces business's cost for posting advertisements and the clear hotel's orientation shows hotels' positive image which might increase employees' recognition toward the business. Sustainability in business is the growth in lively processes which enable people to understand the potential to protect the Earth's existent support systems. Well, looking to the future today's green concerns will definitely become facet of more synchronized business environment, perhaps the concerns discussed in this study, may exchange a few words which hotels may consider in near future to widen awareness and improve business model.

Keywords : Environmental Protection, Green Hotel Concept, Hotel Industry, Sustainability.

Conference Title : ICEP 2014 : International Conference on Electronic Publications

Conference Location : journal city, WASET

Conference Dates : November 23-23, 2014